

TOPOLOGY OPTIMIZATION OF A 41CR4 STEEL CONNECTING ROD FOR A DEUTZ F4L912 TRACTOR ENGINE USING THE SIMP METHOD

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ABSTRACT: The current research presents a novel approach involving design enhancement and topology optimization analysis of the Deutz F4L912 tractor engine connecting rod. Aiming to significantly decrease mass while preserving structural integrity under tensile loads by implementing a streamlined workflow utilizing FreeCAD, Gmsh, PrePoMax/CalculiX, and a Python-driven SIMP (Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization) loop. The optimized rod exhibits a projected 20% mass reduction while retaining similar structural performance, as confirmed by compliance, stress distribution, and mass savings analyses. This study provides manufacturers with a cost-effective methodology for improving mechanical component design, enabling substantial resource savings via mass minimization.

KEYWORDS: Connecting rod, simp, optimization, simulation, Deutz F4L912.,

1 INTRODUCTION

The Algerian company ETRAG (Entreprise Publique Economique des Tracteurs Agricoles), a key national player in the agricultural machinery sector since its inception in 2009, has enhanced its technological proficiencies through a substantial industrial partnership with the global leader AGCO Massey Ferguson (AGCO, 2012). This collaboration led to the establishment of the Algerian Tractors Company (ATC) Spa joint venture in 2012, with a shareholder structure including ETRAG (36%), local partner Pmat (15%), and Massey Ferguson (41%) (Mahmoudi, 2012).

With a legacy of producing over 112,000 tractors since 1974 under the Sonacome label, ETRAG is dedicated to the continuous improvement of its key mechanical components as part of its commitment to engineering excellence (Ayanoglu, 2023). This study focuses on the redesign of a vital engine component: the connecting rod. As a critical moving part in a diesel engine (Wang et al, 2019), the connecting rod is subjected to significant mechanical stresses. Therefore, its design presents a complex engineering challenge: to achieve minimal weight and cost while

ensuring sufficient strength to withstand peak loads (Chattopadhyay, 2010). This optimization is crucial for enhancing the overall efficiency and durability of ETRAG's tractor line.

Fig.1 ETRAG Tractor

In response to the persistent demand for more cost-effective and material-efficient manufacturing processes (Okorie et al, 2023) (Sabiston et al, 2020), advanced design techniques are becoming increasingly important. Topology optimization (TO) has emerged as a powerful method, particularly in conjunction with additive manufacturing (AM), as it enables the creation of intricate, lightweight components with optimized material distribution,

without compromising mechanical performance (Kazybek, 2021). The Finite Element Method (FEM) is an indispensable tool in this context, providing the analytical framework to assess structural integrity, simulate stress distribution, and validate the optimized design to prevent failure (Decker et al, 2023). While research on connecting rod optimization is extensive, studies focusing on low-speed diesel engines are less common (Gu et al, 2022) (Ivanov et al, 2022). These engines feature large and expensive connecting rods, and any failure can lead to significant financial losses, potentially compromising the entire engine (Li et al, 2021) (Liu et al, 2022). Therefore, there is a pressing need for advanced analysis of the forces and stresses in these components, taking into account the latest developments in numerical techniques (Chmielowiec et al, 2025). Furthermore, it is essential to consider manufacturing constraints, such as those associated with forging and casting, to ensure that the optimized designs are practical for production (Nainaragaram et al, 2025). The quality control of each manufacturing step is also critical, as deformations exceeding tolerance limits can lead to the rejection of parts (Jiang et al, 2024). Comprehensive material selection, aided by educational tools like (CES Edu Pack, 2009), is also a key aspect of this process.

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) has proven to be a reliable method (Rao, 2017) for predicting the service life of engine components. For instance, a fatigue analysis of a 42CrMoA steel connecting rod for a low-speed diesel engine, using a 3D model under maximum explosive pressure, demonstrated that the component's alternating stress (340 MPa) was safely below its fatigue limit (430-540 MPa) (Helal et al, 2020). This study builds upon such findings by presenting a comprehensive workflow for the design and optimization of a connecting rod for the Deutz F4L912 tractor engine.

Fig. 2 HETRAG Heated connecting rod.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Python and CalculiX architecture integration

A central contribution of this research is a modular, automated framework that uses Python to control the open-source FEA solver, CALCULIX. We treat the solver as a "black box" that can be called from the command line, which allows us to automate complex and repetitive analyses like topology optimization. The framework is designed as a flexible, file-based system, with Python acting as the main controller. It handles everything from preparing the input and running the solver to processing the output. The entire process is built on a three-stage cycle for each optimization iteration: generating the input, executing the solver, and parsing the results.

2.1.1 The Iterative Workflow

The optimization process runs as an automated loop, with Python scripts managing the data and execution calls. Figure 3 provides a flowchart illustrating a single iteration of this loop.

Fig. 3 Python Optimization Loop

The entire optimization process follows a programmatic loop, where Python scripts manage the flow of data and execution calls. The previous flowchart Figure 3 illustrates a single iteration.

2.1.2 Dynamic Input Generation

Our framework dynamically generates a unique CALCULIX input file for each iteration, which is the primary mechanism for passing the changing design variables (the element densities) to the FEA solver.

The process (handled by the modify input with element properties) method, involves:

1. Reading a base input file template provided by the user.
2. For each element in the mesh, the script calculates a penalized Young's Modulus using the SIMP formula.
3. It then programmatically writes a complete, valid input file.

```
1 *Material, name=ELEM_MAT_101
2 *Elastic
3 1.87e+11, 0.3 // Penalized Young's Modulus for this element
4 *Solid section, elset=ELEM_101, material=ELEM_MAT_101
5 *Elset, elset=ELEM_101
6 101,
```

Fig. 4 Example snippet generated for element 101

This dynamic generation makes it possible to simulate the continuous material distribution of the optimization algorithm using a discrete FEA solver.

2.1.3 Solver Execution via Subprocess

Once the iteration-specific input file is created, Python executes the CALCULIX solver using the built-in subprocess module.

```
1 # From optimizer_model.py
2 subprocess.run([ccx path, inp name], capture
output=True, text=True, check=True)
```

This approach has several key advantages:

Decoupling: The Python code is not directly linked to the CalculiX library. The solver is an independent executable, which makes the framework highly modular. One could, in principle, swap CalculiX for another command-line FEA solver with minimal changes to the orchestration logic.

Portability: The framework is designed to be portable and can be run on any operating system that supports both Python and CALCULIX.

Error Handling: The subprocess module allows for the capture of standard output (stdout) and standard error (stderr) from the solver. This is essential for logging the solver's progress and diagnosing convergence issues or other FEA errors, which is critical for robust scientific work.

2.1.4 Results Parsing and Data Extraction

CalculiX writes its results to a binary .frd file, which is not directly compatible with standard Python data analysis libraries. To bridge this gap, the architecture includes a results-processing stage:

1. **Conversion:** A utility script (frd_to_vtu.py) is first called to convert the proprietary .frd file into the widely supported Visualization Toolkit (.vtu) format.

2. **Extraction:** The .vtu file is then read into the Python environment using the meshio and pyvista libraries. These powerful libraries can parse the mesh geometry, nodal data, and cell data from the file.

3. **Data Availability:** The critical results—such as nodal displacements, reaction forces, and elemental stresses/strains are extracted and loaded into NumPy arrays. This makes the quantitative results of the FEA simulation available in memory for the subsequent optimization steps (i.e., calculating compliance and updating densities).

By managing this entire workflow, the Python framework effectively converts a static, single-run FEA tool into a dynamic engine capable of performing complex, iterative design optimization automatically. The use of open-source tools provides an available and adaptable platform for advanced structural analysis and research.

2.2 Optimizer model main formulas

Here are the formulas and equations from the optimizer_model.py file, which is responsible for the topology optimization process.

2.2.1 Penalized Young's Modulus (SIMP method)

The core of the SIMP (Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization) method is the formula that relates an element's density to its Young's modulus. This is used to "penalize" intermediate densities, pushing the design towards a black-and-white (solid/void) solution.

$$E_e = (\rho_e^p) \cdot E_0 \quad (1)$$

Where:

E_e : The penalized Young's modulus of element e.

ρ_e : The relative density of element e (a value between 0.001 and 1.0).

p : The penalty factor (a value typically greater than 1, often 3).

E_0 : The base Young's modulus of the solid material.

2.2.2 Compliance Calculation

Compliance quantifies the structural flexibility. In structural optimization, the aim is frequently to minimize and reduce compliance, which corresponds to maximizing and optimizing global stiffness.

$$C = \sum (F_i \cdot U_i) \quad (2)$$

Where:

C : The total compliance of the structure.

F_i : The reaction force at node i.
 U_i : The displacement at node i.
 The sum is over all nodes i where boundary conditions are applied.

2.2.3 Element Volume Calculation

To determine the total volume of the design space and the volume of the optimal structure, the volume of each individual element must be established. The code specifically handles C3D4 elements (4-node linear tetrahedrons).

$$V = \left(\frac{1}{6}\right) |det([v21, v31, v41])| \quad (3)$$

Where:

V : The volume of the tetrahedron.
 $v21, v31, v41$: Vectors from one node (e.g., p1) to the other three nodes (p2, p3, p4) of the tetrahedron.
 $det()$: The determinant of the matrix formed by these three vectors.

2.2.4 Strain Energy Density

Strain energy density refers to the quantity of strain energy retained per unit volume of a material. It is utilized to compute the sensitivities in the Optimality Criteria update.

$$U_e = \sum(\sigma_{ij} \cdot \epsilon_{ij}) \quad (4)$$

Where:

U_e : Strain energy density of element e.
 σ_{ij} : Components of the stress tensor.
 ϵ_{ij} : Components of the strain tensor.
 The sum is over all components of the stress and strain tensors (e.g., xx, yy, zz, xy, yz, zx).

2.2.5 Sensitivities Calculation Optimality Criteria

The sensitivity of an element is a measure of how much the overall compliance of the structure changes with respect to a change in that element's density. It's a key component of the Optimality Criteria update rule.

$$S_e = U_e \cdot V_e \quad (5)$$

S_e : The sensitivity of element e.
 V_e : The volume of element e.

The Optimality Criteria (OC) method is an iterative approach to update the element densities for minimizing compliance subject to a volume constraint. Here the update Rule (conceptual):

$$\rho_{new} = \rho_{old} \cdot (B_e)^{(1/p)} \quad (6)$$

Where B_e is a factor related to the element's sensitivity and a Lagrange multiplier (lambda) that represents the constraint on the total volume. The implementation uses a bisection method to find the correct lambda that satisfies the target volume fraction.

2.3 Characteristics and material properties

The component under study is part of the Deutz F4L912 (also known as the CIRT A type) diesel engine. This four-stroke, air-cooled engine features four inline cylinders and delivers 49 kW of power at its nominal operating speed of 2300 rpm. A peak torque of 215.8 N.m with a 6% torque rise further defines its performance. The engine's key physical specifications include a 100 mm bore and a 120 mm stroke, an inline injection pump, and a specific fuel consumption of 212 g/kWh.

Fig. 5 Deutz engine type F4L912

The connecting rod under study has a center-to-center length of 216 mm. The big end (crankshaft side) features an inner diameter of 64 mm and a thickness of 33.6 mm, while the small end (piston pin side) has a corresponding inner diameter of 38 mm and a thickness of 36.2 mm.

Table 1. Mechanical Properties of Material 41CR4

Property	Value	Units
Density	7.81E-09	t/mm ³
Young's Modulus	210000	MPa
Poisson's Ratio	0.28	Unitless
Elastic Limit	560	MPa
Ultimate Tensile S	800	MPa

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 3D Conception and Mesh

Using the layouts from ETRAG, a 3D model of the connecting rod was created and exported as a STEP file. The file was then imported into GMSH to prepare the mesh for finite element analysis. Structural analysis is used to simulate CAD models in order to comprehend their displacement, deformation, etc. A technique for examining behavior under static loading situations that depends on mesh, boundary conditions, and material parameters is structural analysis [8].

Fig. 6 F4L912 Deutz engine meshed using GMSH.

The final mesh, comprising 133,845 tetrahedral elements and 31,972 nodes, evaluated for quality to ensure an accurate and stable numerical solution. The average Scaled Jacobian of the elements was 0.82, with a minimum value of 0.28, indicating that all elements formed and without inversion. Additional quality metrics, such as the average SICN (0.79) and Gamma (0.76) as shown in Figure 7, further validated the high quality of the mesh, deeming it suitable for the subsequent finite element analysis and topology optimization.

Fig. 7 Connecting rod mesh quality SICN, Gamma, SIGE.

3.2 Initial static simulation

Finite element analysis (FEA) is a crucial instrument for designing functional mechanical components (Zitouni et al, 2021). Therefore, in this section, the .input file of the meshed part was imported into PrePoMax to define the material (41CR4) and boundary conditions. The boundary conditions involved fixing the piston pin and applying a surface traction force of 32,346 N on the big end (see Figure 8).

Fig. 8 Fixation and loading areas

Before starting the first static simulation process, we will export the initial model inp file of CalculiX that contains the geometry, mesh, material, and boundary conditions for the subsequent optimization simulation process.

After running the solver, the visualization of the result will be seen directly on the FRD file generated by PrePoMax. Figure 9 illustrates the displacements, stress mises, strain mises, and reaction forces.

Fig. 9 Initial static simulation results

3.3 SIMP Optimization results

The initial model input file can now be loaded into the optimizer, with the following configurations set: 100 max iterations, 0.8 volume fraction to achieve 20% mass reduction, 3.0 Penalty, 1e-3 Tolerance, and 0.9 initial density.

Fig. 10 Convergence plots

The compliance history indicates that the optimization algorithm converged successfully and rapidly, attaining a stable minimal compliance value of approximately 3000 within the first 15–20 iterations.

The volume fraction history shows that the algorithm effectively managed the material constraint, converging to a steady volume fraction following an initial period of oscillation.

The final density distribution histogram clearly reveals a discrete, "0-1" answer. Most elements have either completely solidified (density ≈ 1) or become void (density ≈ 0), with a little quantity of intermediate "gray" material. This confirms that the optimization has produced a distinct and well-defined structural topology appropriate for interpretation and manufacturing.

Fig. 11 Nodal data results.

Figure 11 (a) displays the displacement of the connecting rod's surface, with the axes showing the displacement in the X, Y, and Z directions. The color-contoured surface exhibits a highly localized distortion, where a prominent yellow peak represents the maximum positive displacement in the Z-direction, and a dark blue depression indicates the maximum negative displacement. This pattern of concentrated deformation is characteristic of contact stress areas, such as the bearing surfaces of the connecting rod's small and large ends. The negligible displacement over the remainder of the surface demonstrates that the optimized shape has effectively maintained its structural rigidity away from the points of direct load application.

The plot Figure 11 (b) shows the reaction forces on the component's surface. The surface displays a complex distribution of forces, with multiple regions of high negative reaction forces (dark blue valleys) and a notable positive reaction force in the Z-direction (yellow peak). These forces represent the material's intrinsic response to the applied loads and the resulting displacements shown in the left plot.

Fig. 12 Normal strain components (EXX, EYY, EZZ).

Figure 12 plots the relationship between elemental density and normal strains, with each point representing an individual element in the finite element model. A clear pattern emerges as a function

of density. For elements with low densities (approaching 0.0), the strain values are tightly clustered around zero; this is expected, as these "void" elements have negligible stiffness and do not contribute significantly to the load-bearing structure.

As the density increases, the scatter in strain values becomes more pronounced, and at a density of 1.0—representing the final solid material—the distribution of strain is at its widest.

- The EYY component (orange) exhibits the largest range, with values extending from approximately -0.0004 to 0.0006. This indicates that the structure experiences the highest magnitudes of both tensile and compressive strain along the Y-axis.
- The EXX component (blue) also shows a significant spread at full density, primarily in the negative (compressive) domain.
- The EZZ component (green) shows a much tighter distribution around zero compared to the other two normal strains, suggesting that the loading conditions induce less strain in the Z-direction.

Fig. 13 Shear strain components (EXY, EYZ, EZX).

The plot on Fig. 13 displays the distribution of the shear strain components (EXY, EYZ, EZX) against elemental density. In stark contrast to the normal strains, the shear strain components are consistently and tightly clustered around zero across the entire density range from 0.0 to 1.0. Even for the fully dense elements at Density = 1.0, the magnitude of the shear strains is significantly smaller than that of the dominant normal strains. The vertical spread of points at Density = 1.0 is minimal. This indicates that the optimized design effectively minimizes shear deformation throughout the component. The load paths established during optimization primarily induce axial stresses (tension and compression) rather than shear stresses.

Fig. 14 Results of the optimized connecting rod.

Figure 14 captures an intermediate iteration of the topology optimization process, where the main structure is depicted in solid red (density ≈ 1.0). The multi-colored elements represent the active optimization front, where the algorithm is iteratively removing material. These "gray" elements, which have intermediate densities ranging from 0.2 to 0.8, are concentrated in the high-stress regions surrounding the bores. This demonstrates how the algorithm meticulously refines the component's boundaries to satisfy the specified stiffness and volume constraints.

One limitation of the current optimization process was the removal of the piston pin. The algorithm incorrectly identified this area as removable because it is a fixed region with zero displacement. Since the piston pin is a critical functional part of the connecting rod, this is an issue to be addressed. Future work will involve updating the code to designate such critical areas as "frozen zones," preventing the algorithm from removing them.

4 CONCLUSION

This research successfully demonstrated the application of SIMP-based topology optimization for the light weighting of a 41Cr4 steel connecting rod, achieving a 20% reduction in mass while maintaining structural integrity. The analysis of the optimized design revealed that the primary load-bearing regions of the structure are composed of solid material (density = 1.0), indicating an efficient distribution of material. Furthermore, the results showed that the component is designed to handle loads primarily through normal strains (tension and compression), with minimal shear effects, which is characteristic of a robust and efficient structural design.

The final optimized design was validated using finite element analysis, which confirmed that the

maximum operational stresses (approximately 150 MPa) remained comfortably within the material's elastic limit. The optimization process yielded a stable and discrete topology, demonstrating the effectiveness of the computational methodology. This study confirms that generative design can significantly enhance the performance-to-weight ratio of critical engine components, thereby facilitating the development of more efficient and cost-effective agricultural machinery. Future research should focus on the fatigue life prediction and experimental validation of a physical prototype.

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6 NOTATION

The following symbols are used in this paper:

SIMP =Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization

Inp = input file

E_e =The penalized Young's modulus of element e.

ρ_e =The relative density of element e.

p =The penalty factor.

E_0 =The base Young's modulus of the solid material.

C =The total compliance of the structure.

F_i =The reaction force at node i.

U_i =The displacement at node i.

V =The volume of the tetrahedron.

v_{21}, v_{31}, v_{41} =Vectors from one node.

U_e = Strain energy density of element e.

σ_{ij} = Components of the stress tensor.

ε_{ij} =Components of the strain tensor.

S_e = The sensitivity of element e.

V_e = The volume of element e.